

Right Libertarian Theory of History. Part II: The State as negation of private property

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Abstract

The fact that politics determines the economy implies that economic production cannot exist if individuals are not organized as a society. However, for society to exist, it needs an authority to organize and direct it—that is, to govern it. This means that society is nothing other than the political organization of individuals. But the state is not the only possible form of government; a non-state or libertarian government is also feasible. In this sense, it is argued that libertarian capitalism is a form of political organization that is neither minarchist nor anarchist, but a government that is established from the free association of individuals, without coercion. Finally, it is argued that the state is the negation of private property by monopolizing absolute ownership of land, and every individual living within the borders of its territory is merely a tenant without the right to absolute ownership.

Keywords: Government, Authority, Politics, Libertarian Capitalism, Minarchism, Anarchism.

The economy as an effect of politics

The theoretical error of asserting that economics determines politics is not only a problem within Marxist theory; it is also deeply ingrained among free-market theorists. This problem, present in classical liberals and right-libertarians, can be attributed to the persistent influence of Marxism within their theoretical frameworks. The first important case is that of Hayek, since in his studies he took as a reference the Marxist theory of structure and superstructure to address legal relations in society. In his words, the public law of the State belongs to the superstructure: “Public law is the law of organisation, of the superstructure of government originally erected only to ensure the enforcement of private law” (Hayek, 1990: 78). Hayek’s reference to government and its laws, as elements of superstructure, implies that he tacitly accepts the Marxists thesis that the economy is the structure that determines the political superstructure of society.

Similarly, Milton Friedman fell into that theoretical error by arguing that political freedom is a consequence of economic freedom: “In the second place, economic freedom is also an

indispensable means toward the achievement of political freedom” (Friedman, 2002: 8). There is also the case of Frank Chodorov, who denied that the economy is causally subordinate to politics; on the contrary, he maintained that the economy determines politics: “The assumption that economics is subservient to politics stems from a logical fallacy. (...) The evidence is that economics influences the character of politics, rather than the other way around.” (Chodorov, 1959: 5). However, the relationship is inverse; the structure is politics, and the economy is its superstructure. Every change in the legal relations of property rights determines the functioning of the economic system. The causal relationship between political structure and economic superstructure is ideological, and not materialist as Marxism maintains.

The economy is determined by property rights. Therefore, private ownership is the universal principle from which all political and economic laws emanate. Without private ownership, free-market capitalism cannot exist. And this was explicitly demonstrated by the economist Armen Alchian, who defined economics as the study of how property rights are distributed: “In essence, economics is the study of property rights” (Alchian, 2006: 69). Now, if politics determines the economy, what principle demonstrates this? This principle is that of organization. Every economic system needs an organization to establish order within the production system. Without organization, no cooperation among individuals is possible. Thus, politics originates when individuals organize themselves. However, for an organization to be effective, it needs an authority to direct it.

Authority as the foundation of politics

Authority is the will that directs or manages the organization of individuals. Therefore, every social system is inherently a political system. In other words, society is a consequence of politics. Or put another way, politics creates society. If there is no authority to organize society, it dissolves. As Robert Dahl rightly argued, every social system or association of individuals necessarily possesses a political system that organizes it as such, whether it is public or private:

“Indeed, it means that many associations we do not ordinarily regard as ‘political’ possess political systems: private clubs, business firms, labor unions, religious organizations, civic groups, primitive tribes, clans, perhaps even families.” (Dahl, 1963: 6).

In the context of business organization, the management led by the Chief Executive Officer is the authority that enables the company’s productive organization. Without the CEO, the business structure simply dissolves. Therefore, in the business context, the CEO corresponds to the highest political authority figure within the administrative structure. Mencius Moldbug is correct in stating that authority is what establishes unity of command in the administration of a company:

“From our experience in the private sector (not to mention the military sector), the formula for authority is clear: unity of command. A single extremely capable individual can manage an

organization of any size, and our society has no shortage of such individuals. From this apex descends the familiar hierarchical pyramid” (Moldbug, 2009: 75).

A very important point Moldbug makes is that the existence of authority, which is essential, cannot be established without a hierarchy of command. Every business management needs a hierarchy to maintain order within all the functions of the productive system, and its abolition necessarily implies the dissolution of a company:

“(…) any large corporation which adopted any management structure besides a simple hierarchy would be halfway already to bankruptcy court, and that simple hierarchical command is the difference between an army and a mob” (Moldbug, 2009: 75).

As Peter Drucker rightly said, the administrative structure of a company is what gives it its existence: “And conversely any business enterprise, no matter what is legal structure, must have a management to be alive and functioning” (Drucker, 2007: 7). However, Drucker was wrong to claim that the administrative function of a company is an economic function: “The first definition of management is therefore that it is an economic organ, indeed the specifically economic organ of an industrial society” (Drucker, 2007: 8). Contrary to what Drucker stated, management is eminently the political organ that command economic production. Therefore, management corresponds to the governance system of a company. Whether it is society in general or a particular private company, it needs a government to maintain its organization. Montesquieu demonstrates the above by stating that society needs a government to exist: “A society could not continue to exist without a government” (Montesquieu, 2015: 8).

Thus, society is nothing other than the political organization of individuals under the command of an authority. This intrinsic aspect of human social existence was described by Freud with the term “horde animal”: “he is rather a horde animal, an individual creature in a horde led by a chief” (Freud, 1981: 121). Now, the use of the term politics as a synonym for society was proposed by Seneca and Thomas Aquinas. However, for Hannah Arendt, this equivalence is nothing more than a misinterpretation of the true meaning of politics, which is of Greek origin:

“This special relationship between action and being together seems fully to justify the early translation of Aristotle’s *zōon politikon* by animal socialis, already found in Seneca, which then became the standard translation through Thomas Aquinas: *homo est naturaliter politicus, id est, socialis* (‘man is by nature political, that is, social’). More than any elaborate theory, this unconscious substitution of the social for the political betrays the extent to which the original Greek understanding of politics had been lost. For this, it is significant but not decisive that the word ‘social’ is Roman in origin and has no equivalent in Greek language or thought” (Arendt, 1998: 23).

While it is true that the concepts of political and social have different meanings in cultural and linguistic terms, in their general sense they refer to exactly the same thing, something Arendt failed to grasp: the social and the political refer both to two fundamental characteristics of society:

organization and authority. In other words, the social and the political imply the existence of a government that administers social relations.

Libertarianism: neither minarchism nor anarchism

Society is a political system, and politics is a social system. In that sense, it is necessary to correct Oppenheimer's assertion regarding primitive hunting bands, since these, although they were not state societies, necessarily had to possess a system of government that ensured the order of their organization without conflict among themselves, so they could not live in anarchy:

“For that reason, primitive huntsmen are without a state; and even the more highly developed huntsmen become parts of a state structure only when they find in their neighborhood an evolved economic organization which they can subjugate. But primitive huntsmen live in practical anarchy” (Oppenheimer, 1928: 27).

The problem with Oppenheimer's logical reasoning is that it reduces the concept of government to the state. This implies that only state societies have government, while stateless societies are necessarily anarchist. It is from this logic that anarcho-capitalists erroneously maintain that a society without a state is a society without government. Randall Holcombe argued that a society can exist without government, understanding the concept of government as synonymous with State: “There is nothing logically inconsistent with a free and wealthy society and the absence of government” (Holcombe, 1988: 280). Similarly, Walter Block uses the concept of government as a direct reference to the State, since he defined the former as a structure whose main characteristic is the coercive collection of taxes:

“What are the necessary characteristics of government? One sufficient and arguable necessary condition is taxation. But this is a compulsory levy; if you do not pay, coercion is utilized against you” (Block, 2011: 742).

On the contrary, the concept of government does not imply the existence of a state, so it necessarily follows that a society can exist without a State and without being anarchist at the same time. Therefore, government is indispensable for the organization of society, but the state is one possible form of government, though its establishment is not inevitable. The state can be replaced by another form of government, but this cannot be anarchist, since anarchism implies the absence of government, and therefore also the absence of organization. Anarchy is the absence of authority, meaning that all individuals live in isolation from one another. Thus, it is concluded that libertarianism is not anarchism, but a form of non-state government. Consequently, the term anarcho-capitalism should be replaced by libertarian capitalism. But if libertarian capitalism is not anarchism, then is it minarchism? Absolutely not.

In fact, minarchism cannot be considered libertarianism. Minarchism, which advocates for a minimal state that only holds the monopoly on coercion and justice, remains statism, not

libertarianism. But what is the reason why minarchism cannot be considered a variant of libertarianism? Can libertarianism defend minarchism? To answer these questions, it is first necessary to define the nature of the State. One of the main definitions of the concept of the State is that of the sociologist Marx Weber. For Weber, the State is a political organization that has an administration that holds the monopoly of coercion, as well as the right to expropriate and redistribute:

“A compulsory political organization with continuous operations (politischer Anstaltsbetrieb) will be called a ‘state’ insofar as its administrative staff successfully upholds the claim to the monopoly of the legitimate use of physical force in the enforcement of its order. Social action, especially organized action, will be spoken of as “politically oriented” if it aims at exerting influence on the government of a political organization; especially at the appropriation, expropriation, redistribution or allocation of the powers of government” (Weber, 1978: 54).

This definition by Weber served as a basis for libertarian capitalists to justify the exploitative nature of the State and the consequent need for its abolition by a libertarian and capitalist system of government. Among Libertarian Capitalists, Rothbard offered a definition like Weber’s concept of State. For Rothbard, the state is an institution that obtains its profits through the coercion of taxation, the monopoly of coercion and the services of justice:

“Let me say from the beginning that I define the state as that institution which possesses one or both (almost always both) of the following properties: (1) it acquires its income by the physical coercion known as ‘taxation’; and (2) it asserts and usually obtains a coerced monopoly of the provision of defense service (police and courts) over a given territorial area. Any institution not possessing either of these properties is not and cannot be, in accordance with my definition, a State. On the other hand, I define anarchist society as one where there is no legal possibility for coercive aggression against the person or property of any individual” (Rothbard, 1978: 191).

These characteristics of the state make it inherently exploitative of individuals’ private property. The reason is that it is an institution that needs to continually expropriate private property to ensure its existence. As long as the state exists, private property can never be fully protected, and capitalism can never be entirely free market. This, in Rothbard’s words:

“Anarchist oppose the state because it has its very being in such aggression, namely, the expropriation of private property through taxation, the coercive exclusion of other providers of defense service from its territory (...)” (Rothbard, 1978: 191-192).

On the other hand, from the perspective of classical liberalism, Ludwig von Mises defended the idea that the state is necessary for the protection of private property and to ensure peace, since only the state can provide government and laws in society:

“Liberalism is therefore far from disputing the necessity of a machinery of state, a system of law, and a government. It is a grave misunderstanding to associate it in any way with the idea of anarchism. For the liberal, the state is an absolute necessity, since the most important tasks are

incumbent upon it: the protection not only of private property, but also of peace, for in the absence of the latter the full benefits of private property cannot be reaped.” (Mises, 1996: 39).

On the one hand, Mises was correct in asserting that anarchism is not a viable form of government, since it is the negation of all government—that is, the Hobbesian state of nature, in which each individual is at war with all others, because there is no authority that unites wills in the form of society (Hobbes, 1999: 88). However, Mises was wrong to say that the state is an indispensable form of government; the state is a contingent form of government, and there are alternatives for establishing non-state government in society. However, the fact that the state obtains its revenue through coercion and that it holds a monopoly on the use of force and justice is not the cause but the effect of the nature of the state. Therefore, what is the justification that legitimizes the state’s right to exploitation and expropriation of private property of individuals? Although it may seem paradoxical, this right stems from the very principle of private property. The state is the true and sole owner of the land, and therefore charges rent to everyone who lives on its territory. This means that no individual truly owns their property.

The permanent struggle between the state and the individual

If someone buys land from the state or from another person, what they are doing is acquiring a perpetual leasehold, since the state cannot transfer absolute ownership of the land to the buyer, as doing so would negate its own existence. The state will exist if it holds absolute ownership of the land. This is demonstrated by property taxes, because if an individual fail to pay this “rent”, the state will proceed with the forced sale of their property. Therefore, the state is the sole and largest landowner with the exclusive right to private ownership of land. This explains the impossibility for real estate owners to separate themselves from the state. Given this situation, as long as the state exists, private property does not exist for the individual. It is for this reason that abolishing the state becomes imperative for libertarians. Only with the abolition of the state will private property be absolute for individuals. This also demonstrates that minarchism denies the private property of individuals by legitimizing the absolute private property of the state. Therefore, minarchism cannot be libertarianism.

It is from this point that it becomes necessary to modify Oppenheimer’s distinction regarding how wealth is obtained. Oppenheimer classified the acquisition of wealth into two main methods. On the one hand, there are economic means, which are the productive and commercial activities of individuals; on the other hand, there are political means by which the state obtains its revenue, that is, expropriation through taxation:

“(…) I propose in the following discussion to call one’s own labor and the equivalent exchange of one’s own labor for the labor of others, the “economics means” for the satisfaction of needs, while the unrequited appropriation of the labor of others will be called the “political means” (Oppenheimer, 1928: 25).

However, from an objective standpoint, the collection of state taxes cannot be considered a “political means”, since taxes are nothing more than rent and other fees that the state charges on all economic activities carried out within its property. In other words, the revenue that the state obtains is also an “economic means”, because it is the same as the profit a person makes by renting their property to another person. Although the state has the right to collect taxes as the absolute owner of the land, the very existence of the state implies the denial of any possibility for the individual to have absolute ownership over their real estate. It can be said that public law is nothing more than the private law of the state, and that as long as the state exists, the private law of individuals will be nothing more than regulations subject to the will of the state. Therefore, the state will always be the negation of the individual’s absolute ownership of themselves and their property.

Given this fact, the only solution for achieving absolute private ownership is the abolition of the state. From the above, it can be concluded that the interests of the state and of individuals are incompatible. The greater the power of expropriation from the state, the less liberty the individual has; and the greater the individual’s liberty, the less power the state has. Therefore, the relationship between the state and the individual is inversely proportional. For the state to ensure its existence, it needs to prevent individuals from having absolute private ownership of their real estate. And if individuals wish to obtain the right of absolute private ownership, they need to abolish the state. Thus, it is not possible to accept as correct the libertarian paradox proposed by Menciús Moldbug. According to Moldbug, the weakening of the state only leads to its strengthening:

“For former libertarians, such as myself, this inverse relationship is critical. The paradox is that weakening government makes it larger. At least, to a libertarian, this seems like a paradox. Once it seems quite natural, you may no longer be a libertarian. (...) The great error of libertarians, as well as many liberals, progressives, etc., is to suppose that the weaker the State is, the freer its subjects are. The opposite is very nearly true. A weak government is a large government – and the smaller the State, the freer its subjects are. Every time you weaken your government, you give it another excuse to become larger” (Moldbug, 2009: 76-77).

While from a logical point of view the weakening of the state implies an increase in the political and economic freedom of the individual, the profound meaning of Moldbug’s paradox is that minarchist position within libertarianism strengthens the legitimacy of the state, since they recognize that no other structure of government can replace it. In that sense, Moldbug is entirely correct. The integration of minarchism into libertarian thought has done nothing but destroyed the foundations of libertarianism. If the state is inevitable from a minarchist point of view, then there is no point in being a libertarian. And if the state is inevitable, any attempt to weaken it will fail, since the state tends to grow permanently (Hoppe, 2007: 15).

Conclusion

Thus, it can be inferred that the general principle governing the history of humanity is the continuous struggle between the state and the individual. This serves as the basis for demonstrating that Marxist theory of class struggle is flawed because it fails to consider that the bourgeois or capitalist class and the working class, neither of which belongs to the rentier or landowner class (the class to which the state belongs), are in constant conflict with the interests of the state. While the business class and the working class compete in the market, this competition is not based on irreconcilable interests, but rather on the interdependence of both classes. The business owner needs the worker's labor to produce; and the worker needs the business owner to receive their wages. Neither class benefits from the disappearance of the other.

Although the capitalist class owns the means of production and the working class owns its labor power, neither has the right to absolute ownership of the land and its subsoil. Only the state is the sole and major landowner. If the capitalist and working classes want absolute ownership of their real estate, they first need to abolish the state.

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